

ON THE ISSUE OF WOMEN'S RIGHTS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: The article talks about the guarantee of women's rights, labor protection, opportunities for scientific and public activities in Uzbekistan.

Key words: Woman, rights, labor, attention, activity, well-being, scholar.

Annotation: V state govorit'sya o garantii prav genshchin, okhrane truda, vozmozhnostyakh nauchnoy i obshchestvennoy deyatel'nosti v Uzbekistane.

Keywords: Jenschina, prava, trud, vnimanie, deyatel'nost, blagopoluchie, uchenyy.

Annotation: The article talks about the guarantee of women's rights, labor protection, the possibilities of scientific and social activities in Uzbekistan.

Key words: Woman, rights, labor, attention, activity, welfare, scientist.

In Uzbekistan, the attention to the issue of women's rights, their labor protection, and their well-being is increasing day by day. Ensuring women's rights in Uzbekistan depends on strengthening the organizational and legal mechanisms and procedures for their implementation, unifying the efforts of state bodies and civil society institutions in this regard, and increasing the legal culture of the population on the issues of protecting women's rights.

The Convention "On Women's Political Rights", ratified by the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on August 30, 1997, is of great importance in further

improving the legislation in this field. That is why, along with other spheres of social life in Uzbekistan, which has begun to build a free and prosperous Motherland, a free and prosperous life, the issues of restoring and developing women's institutions have become one of the most important and priority directions of state policy. In this regard, special importance was paid to the implementation of fundamental reforms and updates that determine the status of changes in the socio-political life of women and its constant growth rates.

Strengthening the role of women in the construction of the state and society, increasing their political rights, and fundamentally improving activities in the field of support and strengthening of the family institution is clearly reflected in the "Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021". Therefore, in the part of the action strategy "Tasks for further reform of the priority areas of development of the social sector", the improvement of the social protection and health care system of the population, and the increase of the socio-political activity of women are defined. It is also determined that it is necessary to increase the social and political activity of women, to strengthen their position in state and community management, to ensure the employment of women and daughters of vocational college graduates, to widely involve them in business activities, and to further strengthen the foundations of the family.

In the years of independence, along with strengthening the factors that determine the position of changes in the life of women, special importance was also paid to the issue of organizing the mechanism of promotion and campaigning among the population in this direction and ensuring its effectiveness. In particular, women's committees, civil registry office employees in cooperation with other official agencies are regularly working to strengthen families, improve family relations, prevent divorces, and prepare young people for family life.

A number of laws are being adopted in the field of strengthening the role of women in the construction of the state and society, increasing their political rights. The adoption of the law "On Elections to the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan" by the Parliament of the Republic on August 29, 2003 further expanded the participation of women in legislative bodies. Article 22 of the law included the provision that at least 30% of the candidates nominated by political parties for the country's parliament should be women.

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